

**OBTAINING NATURAL MEDICINAL BIOLOGICALLY ACTIVE SUBSTANCES
FROM COMMON CHLORELLA (CHLORELLA VULGARIS) PLANT THAT
STRENGTHENS THE IMMUNE SYSTEM OF ORGANISMS AND PROTECTS
AGAINST DISEASES**

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Abstract. This article provides information on obtaining natural medicinal biologically active substances from the common chlorella (*Chlorella vulgaris*) plant, which strengthens the immune system of organisms and protects against diseases.

Key words: *Chlorella vulgaris*, immunity, green microalgae, protein, proteins, lipids, starch, autotrophic, heterotrophic and mixotrophic, lipids, carbohydrates.

Chlorella vulgaris is a species of green microalgae in the division Chlorophyta. It is mainly used in Japan as a dietary supplement or protein-rich food additive. *Chlorella vulgaris* is a green eukaryotic microalga of the genus *Chlorella* that has existed on Earth since the Precambrian period. This unicellular alga was discovered in 1890 by Martinus Willem Beijerinck as the first microalgae with a well-defined nucleus. In the early 1990s, German scientists noticed the high protein content of *Chlorella vulgaris* and began to look at it as a new food source. Japan is currently the largest consumer of *Chlorella* for nutritional and medicinal purposes. *Chlorella vulgaris* occurs as a symbiont in the tissues of freshwater flatworms *Dalyellia viridis* and *Typhloplana viridata*. In 2009, the annual world production of various types of *Chlorella* was 2000 tons (dry weight), the main producers were Germany, Japan and Taiwan. *Chlorella vulgaris* is a candidate for commercial production due to its high resistance to adverse conditions and invasive organisms. In addition, the production of various organic macromolecules (proteins, lipids, starch) varies depending on the technique used to create the biomass and can therefore be targeted. Under more hostile conditions, biomass decreases, but lipids and starch content increase. Protein content increases with biomass under nutrient- and light-rich conditions. Various growth techniques have been developed. Different growth modes (autotrophic, heterotrophic and mixotrophic) have been studied for *Chlorella vulgaris*; autotrophic growth is preferred because it does not require expensive organic carbon supply and relies on inorganic carbon sources (CO₂, carbonates) and light for photosynthesis. *Chlorella* sp. Pig manure grown on digested and membrane-treated pig manure is able to increase the efficiency of the microalgae culture medium in terms of final biomass productivity, suggesting that algal growth is not dependent on the availability of nutrients but rather on the liquid shows the dependence on the turbidity of the digestion stream. *Chlorella vulgaris* is a selected microalgae for several bioremediation processes. A variety of pollutants such as inorganic nutrients (nitrate, nitrite, phosphate and ammonium), fertilizers, detergents, heavy metals, pesticides, pharmaceuticals and other emerging pollutants from wastewater and wastewater, carbonate due to the ability to remove anhydride and other polluting gases. along with flue gases, high growth rates, and simple cultivation requirements, *Chlorella vulgaris* has emerged as a potential microorganism in bioremediation research for environmental pollution mitigation. *Chlorella vulgaris* is seen as a promising source of bioenergy. It can be a good alternative to biofuel crops such as soybeans, corn or rape because it is more efficient and does not compete with food production. It can produce up to 20 times more lipids than crops with a similar profile. for biodiesel production. These microalgae also contain a high amount of starch, which is good for bioethanol production. However, microalgal biofuels are not competitive with fossil fuels, given their high production costs and controversial sustainability. The protein content of *Chlorella vulgaris* ranges from 42 to 58% of its biomass dry weight. These proteins, like algae, are considered to have good nutritional quality compared to the standard profile for human nutrition of the World Health

Organization and the Food and Agriculture Organization. synthesizes amino acids. Algae contain lipids (5–40% of dry weight), carbohydrates (12–55% of dry weight) and pigments, including chlorophyll, up to 1–2% of dry weight. Contains minerals and vitamins. marketed as a dietary supplement, food additive, food coloring or manufacturing emulsion. Due to its dark green color and fishy smell, it is not widely used in food products. As a dietary supplement, it can be sold in the form of capsules, extracts, tablets or powder. Vitamin B12, especially in the form of methylcobalamin, has been identified in *Chlorella vulgaris*.

Chlorophyll is a green pigment of plants, located in chloroplasts of higher plants and chromatophores of bottom plants (algae). Its chemical composition is close to hemoglobin. The biological property of chlorophyll is to absorb light energy and convert it into chemical energy of organic substances.

There are different types of chlorophyll in biology: A, B, C1, C2, D, E and F. We discuss the most common ones below.

A: It is found in action centers belonging to plant cells. They are responsible for photochemical reactions during photosynthesis.

B: Its function is similar to a receiving antenna. They take energy from photons and pass them on to chlorophyll A.

C: It is found in chloroplasts from diatoms, heptophytes and brown algae.

D: Chlorophyll D is found only in a cyanobacterium known as *acaryochloris marina* and in red algae.

As for the beneficial properties of chlorophyll, the list is very long.

It helps oxygenate the blood, thus detoxifying our body.

Aids the digestive system in breaking down calcium oxalate stones. Thus it removes excess acid.

It is anti-inflammatory. Helps reduce triglyceride and cholesterol levels.

Strengthens the immune system. It has deodorizing properties, perfect for combating bad breath caused by alcohol, tobacco or other food products. It contains antimicrobial and antibacterial properties. In addition, the antioxidant properties of boron can be useful in preventing the development of cancer. Typically, these properties are found in a semi-synthetic derivative of chlorophyllin called chlorophyllin. It is water soluble.

Obtaining natural medicinal biologically active substances from the common chlorella (*Chlorella vulgaris*) plant that strengthens the immune system of organisms and protects against diseases.

Chlorella is dried and ground into a powder. The following substances are extracted from the composition of chlorella powder.

Protein, thiamine, vitamin B2, B6, B12, nicotinamide, pantothenic acid, choline.

Chlorella powder is rich in phytonutrients rich in amino acids, chlorophyll, beta-carotene, potassium, phosphorus, biotin, magnesium and B complex vitamins. Chlorella's rich green color comes from its high concentration of chlorophyll, and chlorella has the beneficial properties of chlorophyll.

Conclusion:

Benefits of Chlorella Powder: Chlorella is a high-quality green food source of nutrients. Its basic nutrients are better than others. It has the advantages of high protein, low fat, low sugar, low calories, rich vitamin and mineral elements and some special improvements. That's why chlorella is a high-quality food source such as nutritional supplements and health foods. it helps to dissolve metals.

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